

ENGINEERING SUSTAINABILITY AND MODERN BUILDING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: Innovative building materials and technologies are one of the main forces that determine the evolution of architecture; articulate its new trends and styles throughout the history of construction. At present, the construction industry is undergoing constant innovation, bringing huge building material products to the market. These new materials present a variety of distinct practical applications for designers. The sheer variety of building materials available confuses architects who are faced with the challenge of choosing the right ones for their projects. This problem may be due to the lack of - or sometimes overwhelming - information, which makes the selection criteria for suitable building materials more subjective than objective. The article deals with the problems choice of materials for architectural projects, their possibilities and limitations. It also explores the relationship between innovations in building materials and building sustainability issues.

Key words: innovation, sustainability, selection criteria, potentialities and limitations, appropriation, smart materials and smart building, use and reuse, recycled materials, environmental impact, embodied energy, health and safety.

Innovations in building materials and technologies play an excellent role among the most effective forces that guided the development of the form and style of buildings.

Achieving sustainable buildings is a challenge. Building sustainability includes the design and construction of a "green building" considering both environmental elements, and economic benefits, as well as social obligations to the society in which we live.

The construction sector that contributes to economic growth and wealth society, by providing housing and employment, also contributes significantly to resource depletion and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [2–4]. Worldwide, annual energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions by buildings and the construction sector are 30% and 25%, respectively [5]. The sector uses about a third of the world's resources and generates about 40% of all solid waste, according to

According to some reports, the construction of buildings consumes 25% wood, 16% water and 40% aggregate per year [8]. Some of the most commonly used building materials such as aluminum, steel, glass, plastic and cement are energy intensive materials.

Before the Industrial Revolution, a designer's choice of materials was largely limited to locally produced materials, with stone, brick, and timber being the main structural materials, while organic materials such as reeds were used for decoration. These materials have been used for centuries, and the knowledge required to work and apply materials passed down from master to apprentice. Although the choice of materials was limited, there was a clear understanding properties, strengths and limitations of materials. The built environment has led to a harmonious development, which was mainly based on environmentally friendly materials. Necessity and ease of use led to the reuse of materials from surplus buildings; recycling was often a necessity rather than an option.

With the industrial revolution came change. Rapid advances in the production and development of materials, along with the development of tools and equipment used in construction venues have led to new ways of working with new materials. Designers must understand the nature of materials, their physical and chemical properties, structural properties, their fire behavior, their interaction with other materials, their expected durability in a given situations, cost, maintenance requirements, recycling potential, and others environmental issues such as embodied energy, their impact in terms of health and safety, and, no less important, their aesthetic properties. Determination of all this necessary information about building materials and their constant updating make the choice of suitable materials for the designer difficult throughout the design process.

Sustainable design is the process of designing or operating systems in which they use energy and resources sustainably, in other words, at a rate that does not compromise threat to the natural environment or the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

Although buildings are one of the basic needs of mankind, they are also responsible for environmental degradation, including air, water and land pollution, localized health problems and resource depletion. Buildings Sustainability Goal is to comply with environmental, social and economic standards. environmentally friendly the building expresses a design philosophy that aims to improve resource efficiency and reduce negative impacts on human well-being and dignity in a cost-effective manner.

A sustainable building is one in which technology and practice optimally satisfy the multiple needs of people and society during the life cycle of a building. Factors that influence green building architecture include aspects of economics, functionality, durability, aesthetics, ecology, health and socio-culture.

During the design process, one of the main decisions that has a great impact on sustainable building design, is the choice of systems and materials. Every day, the number of potential materials increases, and in response to competition, new products are introduced, new rules are created, and changes in architecture are created. In addition, existing products are subject to continuous improvements to extend their life on the market.

Problem questions:

- Choice of building materials - limitations and opportunities

At the start of the 21st century, architects are faced not only with a staggering array of materials to choose from, but also with a vast amount of information regarding building materials. This information includes both the physical behavior of buildings and the behavior of their occupants over time. Advances in materials and mass production have given the architect incredible potential in terms of choice.

Conversely, they also require the architect to have more knowledge and understanding of materials and technologies.

- Environmental impact - use and reuse

Construction is the main economic activity worldwide, in which a significant number of people that consume a significant amount of (often limited) resources and contribute to the pollution of our natural habitat, both during the construction process and in the energy consumption of the building during its construction. In practice, it is difficult to strike a balance between improving our built environment, encouraging economic activity, and limiting environmental impact. This can well inhibit or limit the range of materials used, while the pressure to act in a more environmentally responsible manner can lead to the use of new materials or the reuse of waste to reduce the building's environmental impact.

- Implementation practice - expediency of using materials

The architect is forced to take a position in the game between the language of the structure and the language of the shell. For some clients, façade treatment is the only added value they think they will get from an architect's involvement. The obsession with the appearance of buildings means that materials are often chosen only for their appearance and not for their appropriateness.

Methodology

This is literally a scientific critical study to determine the role of innovative building materials and technologies in the development of modern sustainable architecture and green building. It is also worth identifying the most important selection criteria for sustainable building materials. Detailed examples were provided showing the impact of innovative building materials and technologies on achieving a sustainable natural environment.

Innovations in building materials and technologies on the way to sustainable development.

Technological innovations in construction are of interest to customers, manufacturers, architects, builders and building users. Innovation can lead to faster, safer and cheaper ways of doing business; it can also lead to costly mistakes.

However, the construction industry as a whole has a bad reputation for innovation and is often accused of slow adoption of new technologies. Transcendent technologies are the main drivers of the 21st century and the new economy. These include: nanotechnology, microelectronics, information technology and biotechnology, as well as the creation and support of civil infrastructure systems and materials. The most advanced technologies and innovative materials in building construction have been established in the following areas of application:

- Biomaterials - fire-retardant materials and structures
- Thin films - materials for electronics, photonics and magnetism
- Surface and interface characterization - sensor materials and systems
- Nanoparticles, nanocomposites and tissue engineering
- High throughput / combinatorial methods - Cement and other building materials.

Architecture has adopted technology as a sign of fashion. There is a clear link between architectural fashion and the development of materials and technologies, although this leads others to often be open to debate.

There is also a connection between larger societal issues such as sustainability and architectural detailing. The nature of the architectural space, therefore, depends on how everything is done, and for this reason it is determined by the technical implementation and the structural composition of the substances and building materials used. Despite globalization, there are still huge regional differences in construction. Therefore, architects working in the international domain must determine the materials, methods and skills available in countries

in which they operate. The future challenge of developing new building materials and industrial technologies is backed up by the desire to create "green and intelligent" building. Many applications that reflect high-tech developments in engineering practice have been developed in industrial countries that have used smart materials and prefabrication systems to create buildings with improved energy performance, self-monitoring capability, structural integrity, and computerized functions and interactive systems.

On the other hand, many improvements have been made to the practice of know-how, through the development of plastic plant-based to replace the petroleum-derived component and introduce fiber-reinforced composites made from natural fibers such as hemp, ramie and kenaf as the most environmentally friendly materials.

Conclusions and recommendations

Our planet's resources are being consumed at an unsustainable rate. New environmental regulations and societal concerns have led to the search for new products and processes that are compatible with the environment.

Green building technology refers to structures that are environmentally clean and resource-efficient throughout the lifetime of a building, from design to construction. Green buildings are designed to reduce overall environmental impact by: 1) efficient use of energy, water and other resources; 2) waste reduction, pollution and environmental degradation.

Key sustainable building practices include:

- Stable location and location. Avoidance of inappropriate areas such as agricultural land, and the location of the facility near existing infrastructure such as roads, sewers, storm sewer systems and transit, allow builders to reduce negative impact on the environment at home.
- Water saving: Water saving can be cost effective by installing low flow devices that often cost the same as less efficient models. AT landscape applications, you can save water by simply choosing the right plants.
- Materials: Green materials include many different options. More often In general, people assume that "green" means recycled materials. Remember that green material should not cost more or be of lower or higher quality. Most green products are comparable to their non-green counterparts.
- Energy saving: Probably the most important part of green building is energy saving. Through the implementation of passive design, structurally insulated panels (SIP), efficient lighting and renewable energy sources such as solar and

geothermal energy, a home can benefit from reduced energy consumption or qualify as a zero energy home.

- Indoor environmental quality: The quality of the indoor environment plays a key role in human health. In many cases, a much healthier environment can be created by avoiding hazardous materials found in paint, carpet and other materials. It is also important to have proper ventilation and sufficient daylight.

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